

Comparative Analysis Between Conditions of Service and Professional Commitment among Private School Teachers in Ilorin-South Local Government, Kwara State

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Abstract

This study investigated comparative analysis between conditions of service and commitment among private school teachers in Ilorin-south local government, Kwara State. Correlational research design was adopted for this study. Purpose of the study is to examine the relationship between teachers' conditions of service and commitment in private secondary schools in Ilorin south local Government area of Kwara State, Nigeria. Two research questions and five hypotheses guided the study. The population of the study comprise 13145 (7145 male;6000 female) private secondary school teachers in Ilorin south local Government area of Kwara State during the 2022/2023 academic session. The sample size of the study consists of 364(Male 200; female 164) private secondary school teachers selected using proportional sampling technique. A Researcher-designed questionnaire titled 'Teachers' conditions of service and commitment questionnaire (TCOSCOQ) was used for data collection'. Reliability coefficient of 0.85 was obtained. Percentage was used to answer the research questions while Pearson's Product Moment Correlation Statistic was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The findings of the study revealed there is significant relationship between teachers' conditions of service and commitment in private secondary schools in Ilorin south local Government area, Kwara State. Based on the findings of the study, it was concluded that teachers need to be committed to their responsibilities and to achieve this, their conditions of service must be favourable. The study therefore recommends among others that school owners should endeavour to pay teachers' salary regularly and ensure that teachers' salary are increase as and when due.

Keywords: conditions of service, private schools, teachers and commitment

Introduction

Teachers play an important role in educating the future members of a society through their work in school. They contribute to the future of their students either positively or negatively. The commitment of teachers is a key factor influencing the teaching-learning process. It is the psychological identification of the individual teacher with the school and the subject matter or goals, and the intention of that teacher to maintain organisational membership and become involved in the job well beyond personal interest. The greatest commitment of a teacher should be with the students and their learning. Students of highly committed teachers are more likely to learn faster and develop a positive attitude toward school than those of teachers with low levels of commitment. According to Nwadubueze (2013), there is no effective education without a committed teacher who is willing and ready to give his best to his students. A committed teacher is one that is not only concerned about his payment but also sees to it that his students get the very best meaning of what is been taught in class. Teaching is not a mission; it is a profession, and like any other, it requires a certain set of knowledge, competencies, skills, and behaviours. A teacher who is truly committed to students is one that puts students' learning and interests above everything else. It's a teacher who knows that the continuity of the work started with students during the term/semester or school year is essential and does their best to comply with the commitment they have made. The commitment of teachers should go beyond just communicating with their students in class but should include providing opportunities for students to keep in touch with them by way of classroom blogs, Facebook pages, and the like. For these teachers, answering a students' query by e-mail is not a hassle, but a pleasure. Communication is not only made easy but also very interesting not only on the part of the teacher but also on the part of the students. The education of students is at risk when teachers put up a lackadaisical attitude towards teaching the student. Teachers should not allow their personal problems or needs affect their classes. Even when they have to miss work, they should find a way to minimise the effects of their absence on students by: providing a detailed lesson plan for the substitute teacher; whenever possible, choosing a day in which their absence will jeopardise students' learning the least; if choosing the date is not possible, rearranging the content so that the most challenging aspects will be dealt with on a day they will be present. When students don't receive proper teaching from the teachers, their school fees and right are being tampered with. For teachers to be

committed to their job, there is need for proper conditions of service. Schools need to be very attractive and encouraging, if the realization of the effectiveness of the schools is of priority to the government and other stakeholders in education. This is very necessary because, if teachers' conditions of service are not favourable, the teachers are likely not to be committed and the achievement of school objectives may be jeopardized. In private secondary schools in Nigeria, the issue of teachers' conditions of service has been generating a topic of discussion, because teachers have the feeling that they are not well treated by their state government. For instance, in Kwara State private secondary schools, sometimes, teachers get their salary late. Not only that, there has been a serious complaint by private secondary school teachers in Kwara state and many other states of the federation over the new Minimum Wage. The governments in some states, including Kwara State, implemented the New Minimum Wage for teachers who are between Grade Level 1 to 6 but did Consequential Adjustment for teachers from Grade Level 7 to 17. This situation might not encourage the teachers, who were given consequential adjustment (Ademola, 2020).

Promotion of teachers has not been timely implemented in Kwara State, as government do not key in very well to their capacity building, by organizing different trainings or financially support them to attend within or outside the country. To this end, Samson (2020) stated that, compensation of teachers in private secondary schools in many states in Nigeria, especially in the areas of salary, promotion, training opportunities, fringe benefits and other incentives, has not been encouraging. This could make teachers worrisome and could consequently have a negative effect on the commitment of teachers. Olalekan (2017) posited that teachers' conditions of service and commitment are inseparable. If teacher conditions of service are favourable, their morale could be boosted towards high dedication to their official duties and this will eventually help the school to achieve effectiveness in its operation, especially in the aspect of students' academic performance. Sadam (2016) posited that the ultimate goal of any educational institution is to see that its students have excellent academic performance in their examinations. However, one of the ways of ensuring this in private secondary schools in Kwara State is by making teachers' conditions of service such as salary, promotion, capacity building and fringe benefits more attractive, as poor conditions of service could consistently dampen their readiness to making the schools effective. Obadare (2018) lamented that one of the factors responsible for ineffectiveness of private secondary schools in Nigeria is lackadaisical attitude of the governments towards ensuring high teachers' commitment by providing favourable teachers' conditions of service, especially in the aspects of salary, promotion, fringe benefits and professional development.

Teachers' professional commitment is the psychological attachment of teachers to their job resulting in personalizing assigned task by given it their all. It can be measured by affective, normative or continuance commitment. According to Abdulkareem (2016), affective commitment is the feeling of oneness or mental attachment to an organization. Continuance is that commitment one exhibits because of the cost of leaving or losing the job while normative is that commitment due to the similarity in ones ideology to the organization. These commitment leads to school effectiveness. School effectiveness means the extent to which the school has been able to achieve the stated goals, especially in the area of students' academic performance. Adedeji (2018) maintained that effectiveness of schools could be measured through discipline, neatness of the environment, mutual relationship among school members or between school members and members of the host community, judicious utilization of the available resources could also be used to determine effectiveness of schools. However, students' academic performance takes precedence over others, because it is through it that concrete measures could be derived. Gabriel (2019) asserted that, for several years, one could conclude that private secondary schools in Kwara State have not been effective. Evidently, the results derived from Senior School Certificate Examinations have not been encouraging enough as shown from the performance of students from 2012 - 2021 that 38.81%, 69.58%, 29.37%, 36.68%, 52.97%, 26.01%, 49.98%, 17.13%, 39.82% and 48.61% have five credits and above including English Language and Mathematics respectively. Dada (2017) asserted effectiveness of the private secondary schools, especially in terms of excellent students' academic performance, is the end result which every stakeholder in education has a keen interest in. For this to be well achieved, among other things which should be done, teachers' commitment should be enhanced through favourable teachers' conditions of service. It is against this backdrop that this study is set out to examine the relationship between secondary school teachers' conditions of service and commitment in Kwara state.

Effectiveness of secondary schools in Nigeria, in terms of students' academic performance has been a serious concern for the members of the private. This is because the results derived from West African Senior School Certificate Examination since few years back have not been encouraging. Findings in West African Senior School Certificate Examination from 2012 to 2021 revealed the following percentage of students' passes.

Table 1: Percentage of Students who made five credits and above including Eng and Maths

Year	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021
%	38.81	69.58	29.37	38.68	52.97	26.01	49.98	17.13	38.82	48.61

Table 1 revealed that in the last ten years, it was only in the years 2013 and 2016 that the percentage of candidates who got five credits and above, including English language and General Mathematics in WASSCE reached average. However, this scenario is not encouraging and could be due to low teachers' commitment arising from ineffective teachers' condition of service. Thus it is important to investigate the commitment of lecturers as it relates to teachers' conditions of service in secondary schools in Ilorin-south LGA, Kwara State. Hence, this is the gap which this study intends to fill.

Objectives of the study:

The main purpose of the paper is to examine the relationship between teachers' conditions of service and commitment in private secondary schools in Ilorin South Local Government area of Kwara State, Nigeria. The specific purposes of this study are to:

1. Examine the mean response on conditions of service among private secondary school teachers in Ilorin south local Government area of Kwara State, Nigeria
2. investigate the level of commitment in among private secondary school teachers in Ilorin south local Government area of Kwara State, Nigeria.
3. examine the relationship between teachers' salary and commitment in private secondary schools in Ilorin south local Government area of Kwara State, Nigeria.
4. find out the relationship between promotion and commitment among private secondary school teachers in Ilorin south local Government area of Kwara State, Nigeria.
5. examine the relationship between capacity building and commitment among private secondary school teachers in Ilorin south local Government area of Kwara State, Nigeria.
6. investigate the relationship between fringe benefit and teachers' commitment in private secondary schools in Ilorin south local Government area of Kwara State, Nigeria.

Research Questions

The following research questions were raised to guide the paper:

1. What are the mean response of conditions of service among private secondary school teachers in Ilorin south local Government area of Kwara State, Nigeria?
2. What is the level of teachers' commitment in private secondary schools in Ilorin south local Government area of Kwara State, Nigeria?

Hypotheses

There are one main and four operational research hypotheses postulated to guide the study:

Main Hypothesis

There is no significant relationship between conditions of service and commitment among private secondary school teachers in Ilorin south local Government area of Kwara State, Nigeria

Null Hypotheses

1. There is no significant relationship between salary and commitment among private secondary school teachers in Ilorin south local Government area of Kwara State, Nigeria.
2. There is no significant relationship between promotion and commitment among private secondary school teachers in Ilorin south local Government area of Kwara State, Nigeria.
3. There is no significant relationship between teachers' capacity building and commitment among private secondary school teachers in Ilorin south local Government area of Kwara State, Nigeria.
4. There is no significant relationship between fringe benefit and teachers' commitment in private secondary school teachers in Ilorin south local Government area of Kwara State, Nigeria.

Methodology

Correlational research design was adopted for this study. Geographically, the study covers private secondary schools in Ilorin south local Government area of Kwara State, Nigeria. The population of the study comprise 13145 (7145 male; 6000 female) private secondary school teachers in Ilorin south local Government area of Kwara State during the 2022/2023 academic session. The sample size of

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the study consists of 364(Male 200; female 164) private secondary school teachers selected using proportional sampling technique. A Researcher-designed questionnaire titled ‘Teachers’ conditions of service and commitment questionnaire (TCOSCOQ) was used for data collection. It is subdivided into two parts A and B. Section A consist of items designed to collect data on teachers’ conditions of service while section B is design to collect data on teachers’ commitment. The statements in section A of the instrument were based on highly favourable (HF); moderately favourable (MF); lowly favourable (LF) and not favourable (NF) response pattern while section B was based on the four (4) Likert scale of strongly agree (A), agree(A), disagree (D) and strongly disagree (SD). The instrument was given to three experts in the Department of Educational Management and the validity of the instrument was ascertained. Crumbach Alpha was used to ascertain the reliability of the instrument and 0.85 was obtained as the reliability index. This showed that the questionnaire was reliable. Descriptive statistics of percentages was used to answer the research questions while inferential statistics of Pearson product moment correlation statistic was used to test research hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance.

Results

Research Question 1

What is the mean response of conditions of service among private secondary school teachers in Ilorin south local Government area of Kwara State, Nigeria?

Table 2: Favourability of Teachers’ Conditions of Service in Kwara State Secondary Schools

S/N	Item	HF	MF	LF	NF
		F (%)	F (%)	F (%)	F (%)
1.	Payment of Salary	09(29.95)	214(58.79)	41(11.26)	00(0.00)
2.	Promotion	23(6.32)	182(50.00)	141(38.74)	18(4.95)
3.	Staff Dev. Programmes	33(9.07)	42 (11.54)	157(43.13)	132(36.26)
4.	Fringe Benefit	157(43.13)	182(50.00)	25 (6.94)	00(0.00)
.	Percentage Average	22.12	42.56	25.02	10.30.

Source: fieldwork (2023)

Table 2 revealed that 22.12 percent of the respondents (on the average) were of the opinion that teachers’ conditions of service are highly favourable service among private secondary school teachers in Ilorin south local Government area of Kwara State, 42.56 percent were of the opinion that teachers’ conditions of service are moderately favourable service among private secondary school teachers in Ilorin south local Government area of Kwara State, 25.02 percent agreed that teachers’ conditions of service are lowly service among private secondary school teachers in Ilorin south local Government area of Kwara State while 10.30 percent were of the opinion that conditions of service are favourable service among private secondary school teachers in Ilorin south local Government area of Kwara State, Nigeria. Since the highest percentage of the respondents were of the opinion that teachers’ conditions of service are moderately favourable service among private secondary school teachers in Ilorin south local Government area of Kwara State, it is suffix to conclude that teachers’ conditions of service are moderately favourable service among private secondary school teachers in Ilorin south local Government area of Kwara State.

Research Question 2:

What is the level of teachers’ commitment in private secondary schools in Ilorin south local Government area of Kwara State, Nigeria?

Table 3: Commitment among Secondary School Teachers in Ilorin- south local government, Kwara State

S/N	ITEMS	Positive Response		Negative Response	
		Frequency	%	Frequency	%
1	I will do my best to ensure the success of this school	288	79.12	77	20.88
2	If I am given another job elsewhere, I will choose this secondary school over any other	82	22.50	282	77.47
3	I feel attached to this school psychologically	88	24.18	277	75.82
4	It is better to stay in this school because of the uncertainties in leaving for another job	300	82.42	64	17.58
5	The cost that comes with leaving my school is much, thus I will stay committed to my present job	79	21.70	285	78.30
6	The job security associated with my job makes me				

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to love the job	321	88.19	43	11.81
7 The success of this school is of more importance to me than my personal interest	64	17.58	300	82.42
8 Sharing my knowledge with other people makes me happy	364	100	00	00.00
9 There is mental satisfaction derived from helping others through my work	364	100	00	00.00
Percentage Average (%)		59.52		40.48

urce

Source: fieldwork (2023)

Table 3 shows that 59.52% of the teachers (on the average) responded positively that: they will do their best to ensure the success of their schools, will still choose their present job if offered another job, feel attached to their present job psychologically, stayed on their present job because of the uncertainties of leaving for another job, stayed committed to their present job because of the cost of leaving the job, love their job because of the job security, put the success of their school above their personal interest and derive mental satisfaction from helping others. However, 40.48% of the respondents (on the average) negatively responded. Since the number of teachers (respondents) that are in agreement is higher than those that disagreed, it is suffix to say that teachers in private secondary schools in Kwara state are committed.

Hypotheses Testing

Main Hypothesis

There is no significant relationship between conditions of service and commitment among private secondary school teachers in Ilorin south local Government area of Kwara State, Nigeria

Table 4: Teachers' conditions of service and Commitment in Private Secondary Schools in Kwara State

Status	N	SD	r-value calculated	p-value	Remark
Teachers' conditions of service	364	1.94			
Teachers' Commitment	364	1.81	0.68	0.001	Significant

source: fieldwork (2023) **P<0.05 at 0.05 alpha level**

It can be deduced from table three that the p value of 0.001 is less than 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, the hypothesis that states that there is no significant relationship between conditions of service and commitment among private secondary school teachers in Ilorin south local Government area of Kwara State, Nigeria is rejected. Thus, there is significant relationship between conditions of service and commitment among private secondary school teachers in Ilorin south local Government area of Kwara State, Nigeria

Operational Hypotheses

Hypothesis 1:

There is no significant relationship between salary and commitment among private secondary school teachers in Ilorin south local Government area of Kwara State, Nigeria.

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Table 5: Teachers' Salary & Commitment in Private Secondary Schools in Kwara State

Status	N	SD	r-value calculated	p-value	Remark
Teachers' Salary	364	1.97			
Teachers' Job Commitment	364	1.81	0.61	0.000	Significant

source: fieldwork (2023) **P<0.05 at 0.05 alpha level**

It can be deduced from table four that the p value of 0.000 is less than 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, the hypothesis that states that there is no significant relationship between salary and commitment among private secondary school teachers in Ilorin south local Government area of Kwara State, Nigeria is rejected. Thus, there is significant relationship between salary and commitment among private secondary school teachers in Ilorin south local Government area of Kwara State, Nigeria.

Hypothesis 2:

There is no significant relationship between promotion and commitment among private secondary school teachers in Ilorin south local Government area of Kwara State, Nigeria.

Table 6: Teachers' Promotion & Commitment in Private Sec. Schools in Ilorin-south, Kwara State

Status	N	SD	r-value calculated	p-value	Remark
Teachers' Promotion	364	2.00			
Teachers' Commitment	364	1.81	0.66	0.002	Significant

Source: fieldwork (2023) **P<0.05 at 0.05 alpha level**

It can be deduced from Table 6 that the p value of 0.002 is less than 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, the hypothesis that states there is no significant relationship between promotion and commitment among private secondary school teachers in Ilorin south local Government area of Kwara State, Nigeria is rejected. Thus, there is significant relationship between promotion and commitment among private secondary school teachers in Ilorin south local Government area of Kwara State, Nigeria.

Hypothesis 3:

There is no significant relationship between teachers' capacity building and commitment among private secondary schools teachers in Ilorin south local Government area of Kwara State, Nigeria.

Table 7: Teachers' Capacity Buildings and Commitment in Private Secondary Schools in Kwara State

Status	N	SD	r-value calculated	p-value	Remark	
Teachers' capacity buildings	364	24.99	2,11			
Teachers' Commitment	364	24.87	1.81	0.58	0.000	Significant

source: fieldwork (2023)

P<0.05 at 0.05 alpha level

It can be deduced from Table 7 that the p value of 0.000 is less than 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, the hypothesis that states that there is no significant relationship between teachers' capacity building and commitment among private secondary school teachers in Ilorin south local Government area of Kwara State, Nigeria is rejected. Thus, there is significant relationship

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between teachers' capacity building and commitment among private secondary school teachers in Ilorin south local Government area of Kwara State, Nigeria.

Hypothesis 4:

There is no significant relationship between fringe benefit and teachers' commitment in private secondary school teachers in Ilorin south local Government area of Kwara State, Nigeria.

Table 8: Fringe Benefit and Teachers' Commitment in Private Secondary Schools in Kwara State.

Status	N	SD	r-value calculated	p-value	Remark
Fringe benefits	364	1.89			
Teachers' Job Commitment	364	1.81	0.76	0.001	Significant

source: fieldwork (2023) **P<0.05 at 0.05 alpha level**

It can be deduced from Table 8 that the p value of 0.001 is less than 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, the hypothesis that states that there is no significant relationship between fringe benefit and teachers' commitment in private secondary school teachers in Ilorin south local Government area of Kwara State, Nigeria is rejected. Thus, there is significant relationship between fringe benefit and teachers' commitment in private secondary school teachers in Ilorin south local Government area of Kwara State, Nigeria.

Discussion of Findings

The testing of the main hypothesis resulted in its rejection. Hence there is significant relationship between conditions of service and commitment among private secondary school teachers in Ilorin south local Government area of Kwara State, Nigeria. This conforms to the observation of (Mazaki, 2009, as cited in Ademola, 2020), that teachers' conditions of service in schools is aimed at making teachers happy, healthy and duty conscious. Teachers' conditions of service have been found to be indispensable tools in increasing commitment of teachers and organizational effectiveness (Buitendach & de Wite, 2005, as cited by Ademola, 2020). Yousef (2008, as cited in Abdulkareem, 2016) noted that teachers' conditions of service and commitment are inversely related to such withdrawal behaviours as tardiness, absenteeism and staff turnover. The finding from the testing of hypothesis one revealed that there is no significant relationship between salary and commitment among private secondary school teachers in Ilorin south local Government area of Kwara State, Nigeria. This finding is in agreement with that (Ejiogu, 2007, cited in Abdulkareem, 2016) that the typical low income earning teacher yearn is a sizeable salary increase that would significantly enhance their commitment and performance. Fabiyi (2007, cited in Abdulkareem, 2016) also ascertained that of all conditions of service, salary is the best predictor of teacher's performance, productivity and commitment. Fabiyi further stated that salaries of teachers are inadequate making it so difficult for teachers to meet the basic necessities of life, their salaries when compared with other employees with the same qualifications and experience, but are in other sectors of economy such as bankers; site engineers and nurses can be described as unfavourable.

The rejection of hypothesis two revealed that there is significant relationship between promotion and commitment among private secondary school teachers in Ilorin south local Government area of Kwara State, Nigeria This conforms to the findings of Lambert, Hogan and Jiang (2008, cited in Samson, 2020) who observed that employees expect to work in the organizations which provide plenty of promotional opportunities for more challenging and responsible positions. If there is a good environment of promotion policies within the company, employees tend to work hard to earn the promotion, increase the productivity of their work, as well as develop a strong emotional bond with their workplace (Gaiduk *et al.* (2009, cited in Abdulkareem, 2016). Hence, there is a positive relation between organizational commitment and policies and practices concerning a promotion within the organization. The positive relation between promotional opportunities and lecturers' commitment has also been identified in higher education sector in particular. Malik *et al* (2010, cited in Adedeji, 2018) have conducted the research among university teachers in private sector of Pakistan and have found out that academics that are highly satisfied with the promotional opportunities they are provided with are also more satisfied with their job in general as well as more committed to their workplace.

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The testing of hypothesis three showed that there is significant relationship between teachers' capacity building and commitment among private secondary school teachers in Ilorin south local Government area of Kwara State, Nigeria. This finding goes in line with the finding of (Souza, 2009, as cited in Olalekan, 2017) that staff development and training should be an in-built and integral part of school system if teachers would perform their job well, motivated and get full satisfaction from their work. The provision of training and development programmes can significantly enhance confidence and motivation level of educators (Wati, as cited in Olalekan, 2017).

Hypothesis four was rejected, thus there is significant relationship between fringe benefit and teachers' commitment in private secondary school teachers in Ilorin south local Government area of Kwara State, Nigeria. This finding is in conjunction with the finding of (Allender, Colquhoun, and Kelley, 2011, as cited in Abdulkareem, 2016) who found that the workplace health leads to the job motivation and satisfaction. Therefore, the academicians will be motivated and committed in their teaching when regularly receive unexpected benefits. Priti (2009 cited in Obadare, 2018) argued that the role of teachers' conditions of service activities is to promote economic development by increasing efficiency and productivity with the underlying principle is making workers give their loyal services ungrudgingly in genuine spirit of co-operation and the general well-being of the employee. In the same vein, (Ubom, 2002, as cited in Gabriel, 2019)), teachers place premium on variables such as salary, time and mode of payment of salaries, fringe benefits, promotional prospects of teaching and work environment as determinants of job satisfaction, which in turn affect their productivity in a positive manner.

Conclusion

Teachers are the most important resources among every other one within the school system. The teachers manipulate material, financial and physical resources in order to achieve the goals and objectives of the school. It is therefore necessary to ensure that they are committed to their job. Commitment of teachers in secondary schools is more of continuance and normative commitment but it is necessary to ensure that teachers are committed in terms of affective, continuance and normative. Teachers' conditions of service as a catalyst to teachers' motivation, job satisfaction and job commitment must be improved upon.

Recommendations

1. Government should also endeavour to pay teachers' salary regularly and ensure that teachers' salary is increase as and when due.
2. Principals should always try to assess staff training needs, plan training programmes and get sponsorship from government of private individuals if need be. The Government also need to make fund available to the school to carry out needed developmental programmes.
3. Government should ensure that promotions are done as and when due. Effort should also be made to ensure that promotion is based on merit and not on ascription or favourism.
4. Teachers should be given stipends for some extra work done as commendation to make then give more towards the achievement of school goals and objectives.

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